

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue IX, September 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala

PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

THE USE OF SELF-INSTRUCTED ACTIVITY SHEET IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN IN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING

Aurea M. Gajon, PhD

Teacher III

*Leon M. Manigbas Elementary School
Batangas*

Abstract

This study is being conducted to find out the use of Self-instructed activity sheet in Arling Panlipunan in Modular Distance Learning. Furthermore, the research is interested in knowing the usefulness of self-instructed activity sheet in this new normal during the school year 2020-2021.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the factors that affect the use of self-instructed activity sheets in modular distance learning?
2. How useful the Self-Instructed Activity sheet in learning Arling Panlipunan in a new normal?
3. What are the designed program to improve the utilization of self-instructed activity sheets in the modular distance learning?

This study was limited to the seventeen (17) grade five learners. Data was gathered utilizing the research tool survey. The study was delimited to one hundred sixteen (116) learners who have Arling Panlipunan subject.

The study used the descriptive method. The questionnaire was the main instrument used in data gathering. The responses of the study were treated and analyzed using the Frequency and Percentage and Weighted Mean.

Based on the findings, the study revealed that the factors that affect the use of self-instructed activity sheets in modular distance learning demonstrated that majority of the students chose Student's attitude which is ranked 1 at 29.9 %. It was followed by learning environment ranked 2 at 23.5 %, Ranked 3 or 17.6% in Academic disciplines, followed by Learning history and Parents attitude both ranked 4.5 at 11.8%. It was also evident from the table that Cultural differences was ranked 6 at 5.9%.

As to the usefulness of self-instructed activity sheet in learning Arling Panlipunan in a new normal. Among the ten items, eight of them showed a very useful verbal interpretation and only two showed a useful verbal interpretation. This means the learners see the importance of self-instructed activity sheet in this new normal.

To improve the utilization of self-instructed activity sheets in the modular distance learning. The researcher designed a program entitled Project SAMBISIG (Sama-samang

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue IX (Sept. 2024), p.206-207, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Pagkakapit-bisig sa Pagpapaunlad ng mga mag-aaral sa Araling Panlipunan sa panahon ng pandemya).

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13788473

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.